

USING MULTI CORE ROUTERS FOR THE TRANSFER OF LOADS OF DATA

According to an IBM Marketing Cloud Strategy, 90% of the data on the internet has been created since 2016. Every device we come across either pumps or contains numerous amounts of data. So, obviously, the number of data centers also increase. The way this data gets transferred is also equally important. More essentially, these big data transfers are crucial to the maintenance and backup operations of data centers.

So, if the data transfer is made only through a single path, the traffic will surely increase which means there is a rise in congestion. This problem could be solved if a parallel data transfer method is used (as long as the routes are separate). The primary focus of this technique is to diversify and spread the paths available to the e2e(end to end) transport. Integrity is achieved by using a TCP connection.

Parallel routing aims to provide multiple shortest-path routes over different substrates of the topology, as shown in the figure below:

(I do not own this picture. This is only for understanding purpose. The credits go to the owners)

The design goal of parallel routing is to generate substrates that yield the most diverse and non-overlapping shortest paths possible.

Rather than solving the multi-path routing problem all at once, our approach transforms it into two sub-problems:

1. Slicing sub parts from the router topology so that the collection of the shortest paths on each sub part diverse is obtained.
2. Calculate shortest paths.

The latter problem is already being handled in legacy routers (E.W. Dijkstra’s Algorithm helps. An example is provided in the later part of the paper). It is up to the e2e transport protocol’s decision to which one of these paths from the sub part topologies to use with what rate precisely.

(a) Effect of cores

(b) Speedup for 8 cores

(c) Effect of traffic pattern (I do

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Under weighted traffic, Figure (a) shows that parallel routing heuristics achieve higher total throughput in comparison to the single core routing. Also, the number of source-destination flows increase.

Figure (b) shows the speedup our heuristics achieve with 8 cores which works at the finer granularity of edges rather than nodes.

Lastly, Figure (c) shows the results when the traffic is homogeneous, which increases the performance difference between the heuristics and the single core cases.

GOAL: The basic goal of any topology is to achieve maximum throughput (which is the amount of data moved successfully from one place to another in a given time period, and typically measured in bits per second (bps), as in megabits per second (Mbps)).

As indicated in the previous part of the paper that an example of Dijkstra’s algorithm is as follows which makes use of tentative and permanent nodes for shortest path routing.

(This is worked out problem on shortest path routing done by me)

Studies show that the higher the number of cores in the routers, the more the throughput. When routers up to 8 cores are considered, the marginal aggregate throughput can be explored. Further, heterogeneity of the number of cores across routers is another dimension that is worthy of exploration so that new inventions can pave way to much easier way of transmitting data with less congestion.